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Annotation. Cross-cultural communication cannot be perfect without knowledge of pragmatics, although L2 learner has adequate language knowledge to communicate. Therefore, it is important to make language learners be aware of the impact of context on the language they are using. This article discusses the main types of speech acts in different discourses, specifically in business communication.

Key words: speech, speech act, communication, business, culture, cross-cultural, social class

Language learners benefit from the knowledge of the norms of behavior to understand the speech act in a given situation by paying attention the influential factors such as culture, people involved, status and social class. It is essential to introduce the students with the difference of language used in the context, before asking them to produce it.

Students may have some problems comprehending speech or expressing ideas, although they have sufficient vocabulary and grammar knowledge. M.Canale, and M. Swain (1980) claim that this happens because of lacking pragmatic competence or skills. Students may produce divergent language structures or guess the form by relying on their background knowledge. One of the most common divergent forms observed in lower level learners is limited grammatical ability [1.p13]. For instance, lower level learners know some modal forms. They used modal verb “can” for different kind of requests. They were not aware of usage of could or may for

requesting speech acts, therefore, they used only “can” in different kind of contexts. Once I used modal verb could for requesting and one of them asked the reason for my request form, as they thought could as a past form of can only. Then I realized that they had this misunderstanding because of divergence, especially limited grammatical ability. Another instance happened with pre-intermediate level students. They had enough knowledge about conditional forms, however, students got confused when I gave them example for mixed conditional, which was imaginary for the right moment, but its result had influenced in the past. They were confused whether the action meant regret for past or imaginary situation for the right moment.

Overgeneralization is also common divergent form influencing pragmatic strategies of learners. Obviously, lower-level learners often overgeneralize forming past forms of irregular verbs or irregular plurals. However, this divergent form appeared in speech of my intermediate level learners as well. They knew how to link the ideas in speaking appropriately and had some vocabulary of linking phrases, but they sometimes use these linking phrases in inappropriate context because of overgeneralization.

Compliment is one of the most common speech act in all cultures, it can create friendly atmosphere in all situations. As it differs from culture to culture, English learners may have problems understanding and producing this speech act. Request is another type of speech act, which needs to be taught in ESL and EFL classes. N. Ishihara (2010) claims that ”depending on the language being taught, the students’ level of proficiency, and classroom context, it is likely that teachers interested in including pragmatics instruction will need to adapt somewhat the materials they have, or prepare supplementary materials that address pragmatics more effectively”. Therefore, if teachers use authentic materials in engaging stage of the lesson, it will be effortless and time-saving for teacher to prepare and effective for learners to raise awareness of pragmatic norm. The least common type of speech act is gratitude. Asking for permission is also one of the varieties of speech act. N. Ishihara (2006) claims that “if they gain an understanding of the social and cultural norms, they

could still resist accommodating to L2 norms in their own pragmatic performance” [2].

All in all, types of speech acts may vary from culture to culture. N.Ishihara and A.Cohen (2010) view “the learning of pragmatics not only as a cognitive process but also as a social phenomenon, looking into how L2 speakers construct and negotiate their identities as they become socialized into the L2 community” [2.p.14]. Therefore, learners need to learn contextual elements and cultural norms effecting to the conversation in different contexts. As for this lesson plan, the main objective of it is to enable learners to identify requesting strategies and use them appropriately in different situations.

Reference

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